

Simple Paper

Issues of Up-to-date Science Development

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CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

A. Background.

Science is the parent of science, one of the branches of science is technology. It is widely known that technology has existed for a long time or humans have used technology. Humans use technology because they have reason. With reason, humans want to get out of trouble, want to live better, safer and so on. The development of technology occurs because of the use of reason to solve every problem faced.

The development of technology is inevitable because it is a human desire to continue to develop and make new discoveries to facilitate human work. The rapid development of technological knowledge does not go hand in hand with existing human resources so that in some cases it will make this technological development backfire for humans themselves. For example, the development of AI (Artificial Intelligence) or artificial intelligence has recently been intensified by scientists in various parts of the world, without realizing the many positive and negative impacts arising from the development of AI. The human desire to keep developing and discovering new things certainly supports the rapid development of AI, we can observe various sites, programs that have implemented AI in their application, even in small things we can find such as automatic cleaning machines (floor sweeping robots) things that are commonly done by humans and become human habits, there is already technology that can replace these small tasks. Of course, the development of this technology can have positive and negative impacts on human life.

AI (Artificial Intelligence) or artificial intelligence has the goal of creating computers that can think smarter and make machines more useful (Ramadhan, 2011). According to Rich and Knight (1991), artificial intelligence is a study of how to make computers do things that can currently be done better by humans. John McCarthy offered the following definition in a 2004 paper "It is the science and engineering of making intelligent machines, specifically intelligent computer programs. It is related to the similar task of using computers to understand

human intelligence, but AI does not have to limit itself to biologically observable methods." Artificial intelligence is a computer program intended to streamline, solve problems, find solutions based on improved human habits.

B. Problem Formulation

- 1) Problems caused by AI.
- 2) Is AI dangerous for human life?
- 3) Steps to deal with the development of AI.

C. Destination

- 1) Understand what AI is.
- 2) Understand the impact caused by the discovery of AI (Artificial intelligence)
 - 2.1 Positive impact
 - 2.2 Negative impact
- 3) Understand the steps in dealing with the development of AI (Artificial Intelligence)

CHAPTER II

DISCUSSION

A.1 Understanding of AI.

AI is Artificial Intelligence, as AI stands for, AI is a technology designed to make computer systems capable of mimicking human intellectual abilities. AI allows computers to learn from experience, identify patterns, make decisions, and complete complex tasks quickly and efficiently. The public understanding of technology is often only understood as the discovery of new inventions that can be seen while AI is a program embedded in a computer to encourage the ability to develop programming with certain protocols containing programming languages and codes.

Broadly speaking, artificial intelligence is the simulation of human intelligence processes by machines, especially computer systems. Specific applications of AI include expert systems, natural language processing, speech recognition, and machine vision. Various platforms on the internet have emerged such as ChatGPT, OpenAI, Arlist, and so on, so how does this artificial intelligence work? Artificial intelligence works and is created by mimicking the cognitive abilities possessed by humans some of the capabilities that are often embedded in artificial intelligence:

- a) Has the ability to learn things. This aspect of artificial intelligence programming focuses on acquiring data and creating rules on how to turn it into actionable information. The rules, called algorithms, provide computing devices with step-by-step instructions on how to accomplish a particular task.
- b) Reasoning. This aspect of artificial intelligence programming focuses on choosing the right algorithm to achieve the desired result.
- c) Self-correction. This aspect of artificial intelligence programming is designed to continuously refine the algorithm and ensure it delivers the most accurate results.

- d) Creativity. This aspect of artificial intelligence uses neural networks, rule-based systems, statistical methods, and other AI techniques to generate new images, new text, new music, and new ideas.

A.2 types of AI/Artificial Intelligence

Not all AI/Artificial *Intelligence* circulating on the internet is of the same type. Various AIs are built for different purposes. AI/Artificial *Intelligence* can be classified based on its functionality, here is a brief understanding of the types of AI/Artificial *Intelligence*.

1. Artificial Narrow Intelligence (ANI)

Artificial Narrow Intelligence (AI) is the most common form of AI that you will find on the market today. These Artificial Intelligence systems are designed to solve a single problem and will be able to perform one task very well. By definition, they have narrow capabilities, such as recommending products for e-commerce users or predicting the weather. This is the only type of Artificial Intelligence that exists today. They are capable of approaching human functions in very specific contexts, and even surpassing them in many cases, but only excel in highly controlled environments with a limited set of parameters.

2. Artificial General Intelligence (AGI)

Artificial General Intelligence (AGI) is still a concept which aims to match human cognitive abilities in various domains such as language processing, image processing, computational and reasoning functions and so on. AGI systems need to consist of thousands of Artificial Narrow Intelligence systems working together, communicating with each other to mimic human reasoning. Even with the most advanced computing systems and infrastructure, such as Fujitsu's K or IBM's Watson, they take 40 minutes to simulate one second of neuronal activity. This speaks

about the enormous complexity and interconnectedness of the human brain, and the enormity of the challenge of building AGI with our current resources.

3. Artificial Super Intelligence (ASI)

Artificial Super Intelligence (AI) is the concept that artificial intelligence will be able to surpass human cognitive abilities and be consistent with human considerations such as objectivity and subjectivity. Once humans are able to build and develop general artificial intelligence, artificial super intelligence can certainly be achieved.

with ease. Humans expect convenience for a sustainable future.

A.3 The impact caused by the discovery of AI (Artificial intelligence)

Artificial intelligence is inevitable in modern society, especially for students, technical workers, and many others who use artificial intelligence to help solve complex problems related to computing. This causes various impacts in society, some of the impacts arising from the discovery of artificial intelligence are as follows:

3.1 Positive Impact:

- a. Good at detail-oriented work. Artificial intelligence has proven to be equally good at computational problems that require a lot of detail such as solving mathematical formulas, health diagnoses but certainly not better than a mathematician or doctor.
- b. Efficient for heavy-duty data analysis. Artificial intelligence is widely used in data-heavy industries, including banking and securities, pharmaceuticals and insurance, to reduce the time required to analyze large data sets. Financial services, for example, routinely use artificial intelligence to process loan applications and detect fraud.
- c. Saving labor and increasing productivity. An example here is the use of warehouse automation, which grew during the pandemic and is expected to increase with the integration of artificial intelligence and machine learning.

- d. Provides consistent results. The best AI translation tools provide a high level of consistency, even offering the ability to reach customers in their native language.
- f. Artificial intelligence-powered virtual agents are always available. The artificial intelligence program does not need to sleep or rest, providing 24/7 service, as long as the server used is not shut down.

3.2 Negative impact:

- a. Possibility of large data leaks. Many artificial intelligences that require personal data such as Google Assistant, Siri, and Alexa require user conversations to provide relevant answers, so this raises the question of how this data is stored and analyzed. Large data processing allows for *cyber-attacks* that allow for data leakage.
- b. Increase unemployment. The widespread use of artificial intelligence by various industries is often a concern for many workers, for example the use of automated warehouses powered by artificial intelligence will slowly shift the need for labor in this field.
- c. Loss of skills. The use of artificial intelligence will slowly eliminate a person's skills in doing things such as scanning, reasoning, materials if continued will make a person unable to make decisions based on their own thoughts.
- d. Dependency. Various groups use this artificial intelligence to answer or solve certain problems, for example, many students use artificial intelligence to solve problems given by their lecturers, of course this will cause dependence for users who think mals and look for the fastest results in solving something.

- e. Artificial intelligence that is not given restrictions will lead to unexpected things, even Elon Musk, one of the CEOs of the world's largest electric car company, once said in one of his seminars, AI (Artificial intelligence) is more dangerous than nuclear bombs. It is possible that if mankind is unable to control artificial intelligence, there will be a human collapse by artificial intelligence.

A.3 Steps that need to be implemented to deal with artificial intelligence.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has changed the face of technology and made a huge impact on our lives. AI has provided amazing solutions in various sectors, from healthcare and transportation to finance and industry. However, behind all these advantages, there are potential dangers that should not be ignored. It is important for society and policymakers to understand and deal with the dangers of artificial intelligence wisely to create a safe and sustainable world. Some steps that can be taken to slightly control the development of artificial intelligence:

1. Transparency. Developers and organizations should explain how artificial intelligence makes decisions and works, so that it can be understood and accounted for.
2. Regulation. Clear regulations are needed in the development of artificial intelligence so as to prevent misuse and negative impacts.
3. Supervision and control. Artificial intelligence must be supervised and controlled by humans to avoid lopsided decisions that artificial intelligence might create.
4. Providing understanding and education. The increasing use of intelligence allows the misuse of artificial intelligence in its application, such as being used to work on exam questions, so an understanding of the development of artificial intelligence is needed.

5. Emphasizes the natural abilities of humans. In this case, various parties are expected to be able to optimize human abilities in dealing with and solving problems, it is undeniable that artificial intelligence can indeed save time but apart from that all the abilities that humans have are certainly superior in terms of subjectivity, objectivity and creativity.

CHAPTER III

Cover

A. Summary

1. AI/Artificial Intelligence is a computational program created by humans and can evolve according to its programming commands.
2. The positive impact of artificial intelligence can boost productivity.
3. Without being limited and supervised by humans, artificial intelligence can be a boomerang for human life itself.
4. The development of AI/Artificial *Intelligence* must be accompanied by the ability of humans to adapt to using it.

B. Advice

1. Supervision of the development of artificial *intelligence (AI)* must be carried out in order to minimize the negative impacts that will be caused.
2. Providing provisions to use artificial intelligence wisely must still be voiced.

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